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Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of the ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

Importance of mathematical methods and algorithms

Advancing and introducing new mathematical methods and algorithms is critical to ensure efficient use of current and future HPC architectures and technologies. Furthermore, they play an important role in enabling new ways of using HPC systems to address future societal and scientific challenges like climate change. Mathematical methods and algorithms are also needed to allow for new competitive solutions in the HPC market. Finally, mathematical methods and algorithms are crucial for exploiting future non-von-Neuman computer architectures like quantum computers.

Scalable algorithms

Making computer architectures more and more parallel is the key factor for reaching beyond exascale performance levels in terms of throughput of arithmetic operations. While general strategies like increasing the inherent concurrency of applications, the ability to exploit all levels of hardware-level parallelism, and avoidance of communication are well-known, their practical realisation remains highly challenging. In the section on **Scalable Algorithms** the following research priorities have been identified:

- Communication avoiding and hiding algorithms, where new algorithms must be designed to avoid and hide communication beyond the linear solvers.
- Exploiting multiple levels of parallelism: Algorithms have to become more flexible in leverage different levels of parallelism and support load balancing.
- Increasing the level of parallelism: Parallel-in-Time algorithms need to be integrated with spatial parallelisation into applications.

Approximate computing and correctness

An attractive strategy for improving performance on current and upcoming hardware architectures is the use of approximate computing techniques. These aim to improve the performance and scalability of algorithms at the cost of a controlled loss of accuracy and robustness. For instance, today's computing devices often provide significantly higher throughput of low-precision arithmetic operations. The section **Approximate Computing and Correctness** puts the focus on the following research priorities:

- Low-precision arithmetics: Derive rigorous error bounds for mixed-precision algorithms and efficient implementation of such algorithms.
- Lossy data compression techniques: Expand the range of applications where compression techniques can be applied and address side-effects like workloads becoming irregular and unpredictable.
- Randomization: Establishment of tight error bounds for randomization techniques and better integration in numerical software libraries.

Resilience and correctness

Given the increasing complexity of both HPC hardware architectures as well as HPC software solutions, supporting resilience and ensuring correctness are becoming increasingly challenging. Therefore, there is a need for advances in algorithms that allow applications to maintain their performance and provide correct results despite the occurrence of hardware or software failures. Furthermore, with emerging code generation tools, the correctness of results needs to be guaranteed as software development processes evolve. Based on an analysis of the state-of-the-art and future challenges in the section **Resilience and Correctness** the following research topics are proposed:

- Minimise or avoid check-pointing: Design algorithms that do not rely heavily on periodically saving the program's, support scaling on HPC systems, and can cope with heterogeneous architectures.
- Communication-avoiding algorithms: Develop and implement communication-avoiding algorithms to enhance resiliency for HPC.
- Software correctness: Research on correctness challenges that are specific to HPC and its entire software stack as well as on tools that address these challenges.

Algorithms and methods for hybrid mechanistic and data-driven modelling

In various areas, combining mechanistic and data-driven models has been demonstrated to be a viable strategy to model more complex systems with affordable efforts. These hybrid modelling approaches come with new challenges, where research gaps have been identified, as well as create the need for main streaming algorithms and mathematical methods developed for particular use cases. In the section **Algorithms and Methods for Hybrid Mechanistic and Data-Driven Modelling** the following research topic has been identified as important:

- Methods and algorithms for hybrid modelling: A future is to develop and mainstream algorithms and methods that support the implementation of hybrid modelling workflows.
- Dynamical-systems-based deep learning: Improve the understanding of the properties of neural network architectures and training methods.

Numerical, combinatorial, and mathematical libraries

With the advent of exascale HPC infrastructures, the enablement of high-fidelity and multi-query tasks has become more urgent, in particular in the context of the realisation of increasingly complex workflows as well as new paradigms like digital twins. This concerns coupling of different applications, addressing load-imbalance challenges, uncertainty quantification, sensitivity analysis etc. In the section

Numerical, Combinatorial, and Mathematical Libraries the following key research challenges have been identified:

- Multiscale and multi-physics simulation methods: Develop mathematical and numerical software libraries for such simulations.
- Model calibration and Uncertainty Quantification: Establish algorithms and methods for assessing the modelling accuracy

Mathematical methods and algorithms for HPC technologies

Mathematical methods and algorithms are not only needed to advance science and engineering applications but also for creating or improving new solutions for the HPC market. In this white paper, we advocate future research and development efforts for addressing challenges related to scheduling and resource allocation as well as auto-tuning in the context of numerical libraries. After analysing the current state, in section **Mathematical Methods and Algorithms for HPC Technologies** the following research and development priorities are proposed:

- Scheduling and resource allocation: Development of new scheduling algorithms and scheduling solutions that support increasingly important challenges including co-scheduling of complex workflows or resource allocation in the context of federated and compute continuum infrastructures.
- Autotuning: Develop and implement efficient autotuning mechanisms for key numerical libraries for upcoming HPC solutions.

Quantum and hybrid algorithms

Quantum devices, while still in a very early state of technical readiness, start to become part of HPC infrastructures as this supports the validation of new quantum algorithms by also using powerful quantum device simulators. This development will also facilitate the development of hybrid workflows that leverage both conventional as well as quantum computing

capabilities. Quantum advantage is by many considered as being demonstrated. Therefore, increased efforts in research and development efforts related to quantum and hybrid algorithms are required. In the section **Quantum and Hybrid Algorithms** a range of urgent research challenges are discussed:

- Problem embedding, quantum-state preparation, error mitigation/correction
- Algorithms on hybrid HPC/quantum architectures
- Simulation of quantum circuits

1 Scalable Algorithms

To maintain a high level of scalability for Exascale and future HPC systems comprising thousands of homogeneous and heterogeneous computing resources, several challenges at different levels of parallelism need to be addressed. Modern parallel computing resources are based on complex hardware architecture. They are composed of thousands of multi-core processors and massively parallel processing units. Most current algorithms are not able to fully exploit the highly parallel architectures, with thousands of cores and accelerators. Therefore, in addition to communications management, different development requirements arise in order to enable more compute-intensive kernels, related to the fact that the computational parts could be compute-bound or memory-bound.

1.1 Communication avoiding and hiding algorithms

Rationale

The rationale for the severe degradation of performance when the number of processing units increases is due to the important gap between the required time to perform floating point operations by the processing units and to communicate the results between these units and / or to transfer the results between the memory and the processing units.

State-of-the-art

Iterative solvers may dominate the computation time in scientific codes. Two main families help reduce the impact of communication on computational costs. On the one hand, work and communications can be overlapped, as seen in **pipelined** versions of iterative solvers [Cools2018], or by **avoiding communication** at the expense of more calculations [Dammel2015]. By rewriting the algorithms, the all-to-all communications involved in scalar products can be overlapped with operations like preconditioning. On the other hand, asynchronous solvers generally allow for delayed communication and computation by

desynchronizing scalar products—typically used in calculating residual norms—and other operations, such as matrix-vector products, which involve simple point-to-point communications [Magoulès]. The primary challenges are algorithmic, to achieve robustness, and implementation-based, to enable asynchronous communications. Authors in [Yamazaki2017] show that the performance of these solvers depends on many factors, including the hardware, the underlying software libraries, and the configurations used to run the solver.

Future challenge

New algorithms must be designed to avoid and hide communication beyond the linear solvers that have been widely studied, even if this is at the expense of memory and computation duplication (for a selection of possible strategies, see section 3.1).

Sub-topics

In practice, communication avoiding and hiding algorithms have parameters that need to be tuned for a given problem or HPC system. Therefore, solutions need to be developed that assist the user in the required parameter optimisation, e.g. solutions based on an auto-tuning approach.

1.2 Exploiting multiple levels of parallelism

Rationale

The current trend in hardware architecture is towards more heterogeneity, more parallelism and custom features like special compute accelerators. More efforts will be needed to have algorithms available that can efficiently exploit such hardware architectures.

State-of-the-art

There is a need to care about **thread level, vector-level, and instruction-level parallelism** for CPUs and GPUs. Mathematical algorithms, such as sparse and dense linear algebra algorithms,

are among the first building blocks to adapt to the hardware evolutions since they are critical to the accuracy and performance of many different types of applications. Then, it must be extended to a wider panel of algorithms. Regarding vector-level parallelism, the vector or SIMD units can speed up an application by a factor equal to the SIMD register size. The vectorization can be performed with elaborate intrinsic coding or in a transparent way for the application and exploited by the compiler that can detect this data parallelism [Pohl2016]. Moreover, in scientific applications, the load balancing degrades with the number of cores, due to different issues, increasing probability to encounter slower computing nodes, uneven work distribution, or other heterogeneities from the software or hardware. Mechanisms are thus needed to mitigate its impact. On the software side, repartitioning/redistributing or hybrid distributed & thread level parallelization can be implemented. These solutions can be supported by runtime strategies to achieve **dynamic load balance** and better exploit the computing nodes [Garcia2014]. In any case, accurate and systematic and continuous performance monitoring is required [Pop2024]. Let's take the methods based on an unstructured mesh as an example. Adaptive mesh refinement (**AMR**) strategies are software solutions designed to reduce simulation costs by either maintaining accuracy with smaller meshes or enhancing accuracy for a given mesh size guided by error estimators [DiPietro2014]. However, AMR can result in a costly solution in terms of CPU usage and memory management as, in addition to the mesh adaptation, it requires recomputing mesh-based arrays, communication strategy, and to interpolate the solution in parallel from two successive meshes [Digonnet2019].

Future challenge

A future challenge will be the design of algorithms that can flexibly leverage different levels of parallelism and custom features as well as algorithms supporting load balancing.

Challenge sub-topics

The parallelism introduced by SIMD instructions, like AVX2 and AVX512 in case of the x86 ISA or SVE in case of the Arm ISA, and vector instructions, like RISC-V's RVV, is often not fully exploited. The potential of vectorization depends on the characteristics of the algorithms and the data layouts. The algorithms with a complex control flow with multiple branching may not easily be vectorized, and also the data must be contiguous in memory. Therefore, in some cases restructuring the code or relying on alternative algorithms can expose more parallelism to lead to a more efficient use of SIMD units. Regarding load balancing, the software repartitioning is not straightforward, as generally, scientific codes do not have one single algorithm to balance. For example, the solution of PDEs may require a matrix assembly, involving a loop over the mesh elements or faces, and algebraic solvers involving loops over the mesh nodes. Both may have different load balancing requirements, thus requiring a specific and challenging strategy [Berrone2022]. Using AMR on unstructured mesh and advanced numerical schemes is not well-adapted for accelerators. It is for the moment performed on the CPU so that, when the mesh is adapted, frequent and substantial memory transfers are needed from the CPU to the GPU. In the case of structured mesh-based methods, the situation is different as usually they rely on hierarchical Cartesian meshes with main challenges being the mesh hierarchy, distribution and load balance [Lintermann2020].

1.4 Increasing the level of parallelism

Rationale

Hardware architectures of HPC systems will, in order to increase the available performance, have to become even more parallel than today. Therefore, it is crucial to have algorithms available that can leverage the further increasing parallelism.

State-of-the-art

The need for new algorithmic concepts is particularly urgent in fields that require simulating the evolution of a system starting from a given initial condition. Traditionally, the focus in these fields lies on the efficient parallelisation in space, leaving time being processed serially, via time-stepping. While this is a viable approach in many situations, the amount of parallelism that can be exploited is inherently limited by the number of spatial degrees of freedom. For long-time simulations, such algorithms will not be able to fully exploit the growth in computational power arising from future Exascale systems. Moreover, forward-in-time simulation is often only part of the task, representing, for instance, a constraint when computing an optimal design or performing real-time control. In such situations, one usually jointly solves a coupled forward-backward time-evolution problem simultaneously over a complete time interval, excluding the option of time-stepping. Mathematical algorithms for efficient **time-parallelisation** have been a topic of study for over two decades [Ong2020], with methods based on space-time multigrid,

multiple shooting, waveform relaxation, space-time domain decomposition, multiple simulations for ensemble averaging in turbulent flows, as well as direct time-parallel methods such as parareal or PFASST.

Future challenge

The future challenge will be to integrate Parallel-in-Time (PinT) algorithms with spatial parallelisation into applications and push the limits of parallel efficiency.

Sub-topics

Addressing this challenge will require delivering optimal strategies to map space-time-ensemble parallel software to future architectures, including dynamic resource allocation due to space-time adaptive 4D meshing [Belda2009]. Additionally, devising PinT methods that remain effective when confronted with inexactness from various sources (mixed precision calculations, premature ending of iterative solvers, compression of communication), one can improve efficiency by reducing memory and communication requirements while simultaneously improving robustness. On the algorithmic side, there is an increasing demand to integrate time-parallelism into optimization, system identification and uncertainty quantification computational workflows.

2 Approximate Computing and Correctness

Approximate computing commonly refers to all the techniques that aim at improving performance and scalability of algorithms and software at the cost of a controlled loss of accuracy and robustness. By the use of approximate computing techniques, it is possible to reduce the operational complexity, the storage, the amount of communications (either through the memory bus or across the network), execution time or energy consumption; the resulting algorithms must still provide rigorous bounds on the quality of the solution and clearly define the circumstances under which these bounds hold true. Furthermore, multiple approximate computing techniques can be often combined without additional loss of accuracy and robustness, which leads to incremental performance benefits. These techniques are becoming increasingly popular in the traditional HPC domain (e.g., numerical simulations) as well as in high performance data analytics and artificial intelligence and can effectively exploit the high computational power of modern, massively accelerated, supercomputers. Nevertheless, a considerable research effort is necessary to extend their use to a much wider panel of algorithms and applications both on a theoretical and mathematical level, and in practice through robust and efficient software libraries and tools.

2.1 Low-precision arithmetics

Rationale

Modern computing resources such as GPU accelerators, or CPUs including SIMD instructions, with wide registers, are more and more optimised to perform floating-point calculations with reduced precision (e.g. half or even quarter) at extremely high rates. Despite their widespread use in machine learning, these arithmetics cannot be straightforwardly used in many scientific applications because of their low accuracy. This shortcoming can be overcome through the development of mixed-precision algorithms; these employ multiple precisions in order to reduce execution time and

memory consumption with guaranteed accuracy and robustness under precisely defined conditions.

State-of-the-art

Although the use of multiple precision within the same algorithm has been exploited occasionally for many decades, it has seen a renewed interest in recent years due to the widespread availability of very low precision arithmetics and the increasing performance gap between high and low precision processing units. Mixed precision algorithms attempt to use low precision arithmetic for the bulk of computations, while using high precision only for operations that are critical for ensuring a prescribed level of accuracy and robustness. Based on this idea, many mixed-precision algorithms have been proposed recently [Higham2022, Abdelfattah23]. Certainly, the most well-known use of mixed precision is in iterative refinement algorithms for the solution of dense and sparse linear systems or least-squares problems [Carson2018, Amestoy2023]. Other examples include mixed precision eigenvalues computations [Tsai2021] or mixed precision iterative methods where preconditioners are computed and applied in low precision [Flegar2021]. Even elementary kernels such as matrix multiplication [Mukunoki2020] can be computed in mixed precision to take advantage of low-precision units. As a result of this success, some of the most recent vendor mathematical libraries include multiple mixed precision algorithms.

Future challenge

The development and adoption of **mixed-precision** algorithms requires considerable advances in numerical analysis to derive rigorous error bounds and the conditions under which they hold. Many of the mixed-precision methods presented in the literature have only been experimentally validated but lack a rigorous error analysis that provides indications on the achievable accuracy and under which conditions it can be reached. When dealing with very low-precision arithmetics, the unit rounding is

so large that classical deterministic error analysis, which deals with the worst-case error accumulation, leads to very loose error bounds. Recent results [Higham2019] showed that probabilistic error analysis can lead to much tighter error bounds that hold with very high probability and have a much better practical interest. These novel approaches also suggest that the use of stochastic rounding [Crocic2022, Xia2024] can overcome some limitations of very low-precision arithmetics and enable their use in a wider range of algorithms. In addition to the mentioned topics, there is also a need to deal with the narrow range of representable values, which makes the use of appropriately designed scaling methods unavoidable. Furthermore, fixed-point or even integer formats, for which efficient hardware support is already widely available (e.g., on GPUs), will be increasingly used in scientific computing workloads; these require an appropriate error analysis methodology which differs from what is commonly used for floating-point. Finally, the efficient implementation of mixed-precision algorithms poses numerous challenges that relate to the handling of potentially multiple versions of the same data and of operations that combine data that have different storage formats; in these cases naively casting the data can lead to an unacceptable loss of performance that exceeds the expected benefits whereas careful, on-the-fly data conversions can not only reduce the overhead associated with handling multiple precisions but, furthermore, open opportunities for additional optimizations.

2.2 Lossy data compression techniques

Rationale

Numerous high-performance computing applications suffer from high memory consumption or excessive data traffic across interconnects such as memory buses or network. These problems can be mitigated through the use of lossy data compression techniques that can be used to reduce storage and communications at the cost of a controlled loss of accuracy. Among these techniques, we can cite SZ compression methods or low-rank approximation

techniques. The latter have the additional benefit of not only reducing memory and communications, but also the operational complexity of numerous algorithms because data can be used in compressed form in elementary computations.

State-of-the-art

H-matrices [Hackbusch99] are certainly the most well known and widely used example of low-rank approximation techniques. This compressed storage format, for example, can reduce the storage and operational complexity of a dense matrix factorization from squared and cubic to linear and log-linear, respectively. More recently, novel low-rank formats have been proposed that aim at either further reducing the complexity (i.e., through the use of nested bases) or to achieving a better trade-off between complexity and computational efficiency. Among many different uses, for example, these methods have been used to improve the performance of dense and sparse direct linear solvers or to compute effective preconditioners for iterative solvers. Other compression techniques such as SZ [Cappello2024] have been used to improve the performance and scalability of iterative linear solvers but also deep neural networks.

Future challenge

Data compression depends on the characteristics of the problem and is not guaranteed for all physical models. Further research is needed to take advantage of this approach. From a performance point of view, the use of data compression techniques poses difficult challenges because they typically result in an extremely irregular and unpredictable workload, which makes the scheduling hard to implement in an efficient way. Furthermore, the use of low-rank approximations implies operations of low granularity and low arithmetic intensity which are not well suited for GPU computations; batched operations or accumulation techniques may help to alleviate these problems. Finally, software has to be written in such a way that the data format used for computations is dissociated from the format used for storage; furthermore, dedicated computing resources that may

be available outside of CPUs and GPUs, such as data processing units integrated in network interfaces (so-called SmartNICs), could be leveraged to perform data compression without interrupting the flow of computations.

Although the use of data compression techniques has been extensively applied to the solution of linear systems, it can be extended to a wider panel of algorithms. The accuracy and robustness of the resulting algorithms can be assessed through error analysis techniques that share commonalities with those described above for low-precision floating point formats.

2.3 Randomization

Rationale

Randomization techniques have recently emerged as an effective way to improve performance of numerous scientific computing methods. These rely on the use of random samplings or random embeddings to reduce a problem to another of smaller size that can be solved either more cheaply or more efficiently. Algorithms based on randomization techniques are often rich(er) in matrix operations and therefore lend themselves naturally to the use of accelerators such as GPUs.

State-of-the-art

The use of randomization techniques has seen widespread use in computational linear algebra over the last few years [Martinsson2020]. For example, it has been used to efficiently compute low-rank approximations or truncated singular/eigenvalue decompositions [Tropp2011], to improve the performance of linear least-squares solvers [Sarlos2006] or to compute efficient preconditioners for linear systems [Frangella2011]. In other cases, it was used to reduce the performance penalty associated with pivoting techniques in QR [Duersch2017] or LU [Liu2021] factorization methods.

Future challenge

From a theoretical point of view, the use of randomization techniques can be extended to a wider range of algorithms in numerical linear or multilinear algebra as well as in other scientific

computing domains and their effectiveness and robustness validated in actual large-scale applications. Rigorous analyses must be conducted to derive tight error bounds and define the probability with which these are satisfied in practice. These methods have to be more organically integrated in numerical software libraries and provided as an alternative to traditional methods.

3 Resilience and Correctness

Rationale

Algorithmic resiliency refers to the capability of algorithms to maintain their performance and provide correct results despite the occurrence of hardware or software failures, which are common in large-scale computing environments. In HPC systems, where vast amounts of data are processed across many interconnected nodes, ensuring algorithmic resiliency is critical. This involves designing algorithms that can either withstand failures without significant performance degradation or quickly recover from them. Techniques such as checkpointing, replication, soft error resilience, algorithm-based fault tolerance, fault detection, and prediction are commonly employed to enhance the resiliency of HPC algorithms (see [Jia2023] for a recent survey). The goal is to minimise downtime and ensure that HPC systems can continue to operate efficiently even under adverse conditions, thereby safeguarding the integrity and continuity of computationally intensive tasks.

Recent advances in automatic code generation leveraging large-language models and the increased uptake of code generation tools and services have introduced additional challenges for ensuring the correctness of results as software development processes evolve. Despite the additional complexity of parallel programming, dedicated tools for generating MPI-based programs started to be developed [Schneider2024]. These developments may make what some called a correctness crisis in HPC even more urgent [Gopala2017].

3.1 Minimise or avoid checkpointing

Rationale

High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems are increasingly critical for scientific research, industrial applications, and complex

simulations. However, the reliability of these systems is challenged by their scale and complexity. Traditional fault tolerance techniques, such as checkpoint/restart, involve periodically saving the state of an application to storage, which can be resource-intensive and introduce significant performance overheads. As HPC systems scale towards exascale and post-exascale computing, the frequency of faults is expected to rise, making checkpointing at the required frequency impractical. Designing algorithms that require minimal or no checkpointing is essential to enhance efficiency, reduce overhead, and improve the overall resilience of HPC systems.

State-of-the-art

Current research in fault tolerance for HPC has explored various strategies to minimise the reliance on checkpointing. One prominent approach is Algorithm-Based Fault Tolerance (ABFT), which integrates fault tolerance directly into the computational algorithms. ABFT techniques, such as those used in linear algebra operations, can detect and correct errors during computation, reducing the need for external checkpointing mechanisms (see [Jia2023] and references therein).

Another innovative strategy involves the use of multi-level checkpointing [Moody2010, Benoit2017], which optimises the checkpointing process by leveraging different storage hierarchies and asynchronous I/O buffering. This approach reduces the I/O bottleneck associated with traditional checkpointing methods.

Emerging trends also include the use of machine learning for fault prediction and adaptive fault tolerance. These methods predict potential faults and dynamically adjust fault tolerance strategies, thereby minimising the need for frequent checkpointing [Mohan2021, Nicolae2020]. A study on checkpointing implementations in large scale training using state-of-the-art frameworks such as Chainer, PyTorch and Tensorflow was performed in [Rojas2021].

Future challenge

Designing algorithms that require minimal or no check-pointing continues to be a challenge. It involves leveraging fault tolerance strategies that do not rely heavily on the traditional method of periodically saving the program's state. Check-pointing can be resource-intensive, especially in HPC environments, where re-starting from a checkpoint might also be costly. The goal is to balance fault tolerance, performance, and resource utilisation effectively.

The challenge sub-topics include ensuring fault tolerance mechanisms scale efficiently with the increasing size of HPC systems, developing fault-tolerant algorithms that operate across heterogeneous architectures, efficiently managing data integrity and consistency without frequent check pointing, extending Algorithm-Based Fault Tolerance (ABFT) techniques to a broader range of algorithms, integrating new fault tolerance mechanisms into existing HPC software stacks without disrupting other functionalities, and minimising the energy consumption associated with fault tolerance mechanisms.

3.2 Communication-avoiding algorithms

State-of-the-art

Communication-avoiding algorithms are designed to minimise data movement, thereby improving both performance and resiliency. These algorithms achieve provable lower bounds on communication, significantly reducing the overhead associated with data transfers between different levels of memory hierarchy and across nodes. State-of-the-art implementations include e.g. the Communication-Avoiding Parallel Strassen algorithm for matrix multiplication [Lipshitz2012], which outperforms conventional methods by reducing communication costs. Techniques such as non-blocking MPI implementations and cyclic data distributions further enhance performance by minimising synchronisation delays and load imbalances. Additionally, communication-avoiding algorithms have been successfully applied to various linear

algebra operations, such as LU and QR factorizations [Demmel2015], demonstrating substantial speed-ups and improved fault tolerance. Despite these advancements, challenges remain in scaling these techniques efficiently across heterogeneous architectures and integrating them seamlessly into existing HPC software stacks.

Future challenge

Despite significant advancements, several future challenges remain in the development and implementation of communication-avoiding algorithms to enhance resiliency in High-Performance Computing (HPC). One major challenge is scalability; as HPC systems grow towards exascale, the coordination and communication overhead becomes a bottleneck, impeding efficient scaling. Another challenge is the complexity of heterogeneous architectures, which include diverse components like CPUs, GPUs, and specialised accelerators, each with different data access patterns and memory hierarchies. Developing algorithms that can efficiently operate across these varied platforms is crucial. Extending communication-avoiding techniques to a broader range of algorithms, beyond traditional linear algebra operations, is essential to address the diverse computational needs of modern HPC applications. Finally, integrating these advanced algorithms into existing HPC software stacks without disrupting other functionalities presents a significant challenge, as does minimising the energy consumption associated with these mechanisms to achieve sustainable and efficient HPC systems. Strategies to design such algorithms to enhance data locality and recovery overlap in parts with communication avoiding strategies proposed in section 1.1: Partitioning data locally, overlapping computation with communication, minimise synchronisation points, exploit data redundancy, use Hierarchical Design, implement locality-sensitive hashing, employ task-based programming models, batch small communications, develop fault-tolerant protocols, software check-pointing, and other.

3.3 Software correctness

State-of-the-art

Several approaches have been taken to enhance correctness of HPC software, which, in particular, includes HPC applications. There is a long history of research on methods for checking correct usage of MPI (for an overview, see a recent effort on developing a framework for evaluating MPI verification tools [Laurent2021]). Another approach is the use of formal rules-based, machine-checkable methods for correctness assurance. There are still few efforts on adapting such methods for usage in the context of HPC software (see, e.g., [Benavides2023]). At the level of compilers, in particular optimization passes, the topic is being discussed more in recent years [Lee2019], to the point of formalising the code in a theorem prover environment and automatically generating code with the proof [Koehler24].

Future challenge

More research in support of the correctness challenges in HPC is needed, in particular related to HPC software at all levels of the software stack: from high performance network drivers and fabric abstractions, through compilation passes and libraries/frameworks, to tooling for correctness analysis of parallel codes. This includes efforts on creating formal specifications that can be used by verification and formal reasoning technologies. Furthermore, there is a need to augment available static by dynamic analysis methods and extend these to parallel programs.

4 Algorithms and Methods for Hybrid Mechanistic and Data-Driven Modelling

Rationale

For decades, methods requiring HPC resources have focussed on mechanistic models, i.e., models based on theories and an understanding of the underlying physical or other mechanisms that can be simulated. Meanwhile, HPC systems are more and more used for creating data-driven models, e.g., using machine-learning methods. For an increasing number of cases, methods for mechanistic and data-driven modelling are successfully combined. Additionally, mechanistic models can serve as a guide to build more explainable deep neural networks.

4.1 Methods and algorithms for hybrid modelling

State-of-the-art

There are various ways in how the different types of methods can be combined. In biophysics there had been early efforts for leveraging machine-learning methods for analysing molecular-dynamics (MD) simulation data or to use data-driven methods for designing force fields and potentials [Noe2020]. Others used machine-learning methods for steering MD simulation workflows (see, e.g., [Brace2022]). Some of these approaches are more and more used to analyse molecular dynamics data describing chemical reactions [Bocus2024, Ray2024]. Another idea is to apply machine learning algorithms to generate surrogate models to create more complex models that are otherwise too difficult or too expensive to simulate (see, e.g., [Pigeon2023]). There are substantial efforts ongoing to train deep neural networks to reproduce PDE-based simulations [Karniadakis2021] or to supplement PDE-based simulations with data-driven closure terms [Levine2022].

Future challenge

Based on the various pioneering efforts, the future challenge is to develop and mainstream algorithms and methods that support the implementation of hybrid modelling workflows.

Sub-topics

As subtopics for this challenge, we mention the necessity to obtain guarantees on accuracy of the resulting hybrid models, both from a theoretical and practical viewpoint, given the many domain-specific requirements that these hybrid modelling tools face. Furthermore, the efficiency of training these models on given datasets, as well as an assessment of uncertainty in the models are of utmost importance. Few efforts for rather specific cases have been published (see, e.g., [Chen2023, Deepak2023]).

One of the key challenges common to many (often domain-specific) problems is data assimilation, which in this context refers to the matching of data and the state of the model. This often involves time-continuous state update estimation or solving inverse problems, like estimating model parameters for a given set of data.

4.2 Methods and algorithms for dynamical-systems-based deep learning

State-of-the-art

Neural networks are being used in a wide range of applications in classification, noise removal, pattern recognition and so on, because of their excellent approximation properties and ability to generalise to unseen data. Despite their popularity, their reliability remains limited by an inherent lack of understanding of the properties of neural network architectures and training methods. This is a critical challenge for pushing the use of data-driven models and hybrid-modelling approaches in HPC-based computational science research. A recent line of research aims at formulating unifying principles for the design of neural networks, e.g., via a continuous-in-time interpretation of Recurrent or Residual Neural Networks (see e.g. [Haber2017, Ruthotto2020, Celledoni2023]). Such formulations also allow using advanced multi-resolution/multilevel techniques to accelerate training [Guenther2020, Kopanicakova2024].

Future challenge

A key challenge is to increase our understanding of the effect of neural network architecture and training methods on neural network performance and training efficiency.

Sub-topics

Addressing this challenge requires research related to the dynamical systems interpretation of neural networks, multilevel neural networks, multilevel training methods, and uncertainty quantification on neural-network predictions. Such approaches combine the benefit of enhancing explainability with the added computational efficiency arising from the well-established computational science community.

5 Numerical, Combinatorial, and Mathematical Libraries

Rationale

In recent decades, many algorithmic and mathematical advances have been made to minimise computational efforts required for a desired accuracy. The challenge then becomes to turn these algorithms into HPC software on current and future exascale machines and push them to real applications. The architecture of these machines is bound to influence the design of the methods. HPC software engineering and mathematical algorithm development need to go hand in hand.

5.1 Multiscale and multi-physics simulation methods

State of the art

In past decades, substantial progress has been made in high-fidelity modelling of complex physical systems, to the extent of digital twins for real-time control or for design optimization are quickly becoming an industry standard. We mention application in, for instance, in biomedicine, fusion physics, wind farm energy, epidemiology, additive manufacturing, micro-electronics predictions [Sanz2017] and contaminant transport at urban scale. The increased modelling capacity can be obtained in many ways, including multiscale and multi-physics approaches, in which multiple mathematical models need to be simulated together using an appropriate coupling.

In multiscale models, one models the same system at different levels of detail. We mention biomedicine, in which continuum models at the organ level (typically discretized as finite elements, or finite volumes) can be coupled to cellular level simulations (typically individual-based models), material science (where density functional theory (DFT) is coupled to molecular dynamics coupled at its turn to continuum mechanics) [Vassaux2019], traffic flow (in which a finite volume flow model which is coupled to individual-based driver models). Another example, where both models now use similar

numerical techniques, is air pollution in urban regions or in wind farms coupled to weather forecast models [Avila2022]. In multi-physics models, the goal is to couple models of different parts of a physical system. In this category, we find problems like conjugate heat transfer to account for two-way heat coupling and non-homogeneous effects [Houzeaux2024], fluid-structure interactions (aerodynamics, civil engineering), or flow problems with chemically reactive components.

Key challenge

Develop mathematical and numerical software libraries for multiscale and multi-physics simulation.

Subtopics

Coupling libraries are responsible for establishing interpolation schemes and coordinating simulations within a multi-code framework. These libraries must manage various discretization methods (such as finite element, finite volume, and finite difference), different orders, and both surface and volume interpolations, ensuring that the interpolation remains conservative (maintaining symmetry and rigid-body motion in fluid-structure interactions). Numerous libraries have been created for high-performance computing (HPC) environments. Examples of such libraries are: PRECICE (Precise Code Interaction Coupling Environment) [Bungartz2016]; OpenPalm (Projet d'Assimilation par Logiciel Multi-méthodes) [Buis2006]; CWIPI (Coupling With Interpolation Parallel Interface) that is a part of OpenPalm [Refloch2011] [Duchaine2015]; MUI (Multiscale Universal Interface) [Tang2015] and PLE (Parallel Exchange and Location) [Fournier2020].

One of the primary challenges in multi-physics and multiscale coupling is achieving parallel efficiency in a multi-code context [Lintermann2020]. Although Jacobi-type coupling schemes are fully parallel, they face significant

robustness issues. Conversely, Gauss-Seidel type couplings offer desirable convergence properties but are inherently sequential, thus degrading the parallel efficiency of the simulation. A solution consists in fully exploiting the resources by overloading the cores to enable the different physics to share the resources [Houzeaux2020]. Such a challenge should also be solved in the case of heterogeneous supercomputers, where different codes may run on different platforms (CPU/GPU) [Sun2015].

5.2 Model calibration and Uncertainty Quantification

State-of-the-art

To reliably use simulation-generated predictions in science and engineering, one needs trustworthy mathematical models that are calibrated to measurement data. Inferring these parameters and/or states from large amounts of possibly high-resolution data leads to computationally intensive inverse problems. Many methods for inverse problems are formulated in a Bayesian setting [Law2015]: given a prior distribution for the model

parameters, Bayes' rule defines a posterior parameter distribution using the measurement data and the likelihood of the data for a given parameter value, which is obtained via evaluation of a (possibly time-dependent) partial differential equation (called the forward model). Two approaches exist. In optimization-based approaches, including variational

methods, one essentially searches the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimator, i.e., the parameter value for which the posterior distribution is maximal. In a sampling-based approach, the posterior distribution is sampled,

additionally yielding uncertainty information at significant computational cost (since many more likelihood evaluations, i.e., forward solves, are required). Sampling is usually done via Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) [Law2015]. An alternative approach, allowing parallelization of the otherwise serial sampling or optimization, is emerging in the form of consensus-based optimization [Cipriani2022, Totzeck2022] or sampling [Carrillo2021, Reich2021], which can be interpreted as interacting particle systems [Herty2022].

Future challenge

The future challenge will be to establish algorithms and methods for assessing the modelling accuracy of computational models based on measurement data, and quantify the corresponding uncertainties.

Sub-topics

Several crucial computational bottlenecks have not yet been resolved satisfactorily. When addressing very high-dimensional inference problems, the cost of likelihood evaluation increases as a function of the dimensionality of the forward problem. This problem can be addressed using multilevel methods [Dodwell2018]. Significant efforts have already been devoted in alleviating the effect of the high dimensionality of the forward model. While most multilevel methods combine different levels of discretization of the same forward model [Giles2008, Haji2017], a number of multi-fidelity MCMC methods have been proposed that combine models at different levels of modelling fidelity [Peherstorfer2018].

Additionally, the serial nature of classical sampling methods prohibits the full exploitation of current highly parallel exascale systems. Time-parallelism can be achieved, for instance, by considering interacting particles evolving in parameter space according to artificial dynamics that include (i) gradient descent (as in optimization); (ii) a deterministic interaction between the particles; and (iii) stochastic noise. Examples are the ensemble Kalman filter and sampler [Garbuno2022, Schillings2017].

6 Mathematical Methods and Algorithms for HPC Technologies

Research and innovation of mathematical methods and algorithms will also be crucial for further developing the European ecosystem for HPC-related solutions and products. Two topical areas where particular impact can be made is scheduling and auto-tuning in the context of numerical libraries.

6.1 Scheduling and resource allocation

Rationale

The rationale for the topical area of **scheduling** is that future HPC systems will be more heterogeneous and at the same time be more often integrated within federated infrastructures and a continuum of digital resources. Currently dominating approaches to scheduling of jobs or other units of work, and allocation of resources will not be sufficient any more.

State-of-the-art

Limitations of current solutions for scheduling within HPC systems include the throughput limitations, which affect, e.g., large ensemble runs and other high-throughput workloads. Furthermore, both types of workflows comprising coupled tasks as well as heterogeneous HPC architectures with different types of scarce resources push the needs for co-scheduling of work and co-allocation of resources. Recent efforts to develop new resource and job management software for HPC systems addressing these limitations and needs include the ongoing development of PyCOMPSs [Tejedor2017] and Flux [Ahn2018]. Towards co-allocation of resources, efforts have been continued to concurrent allocation of compute and fast storage resources (see, e.g., [Fan2019]). Beyond HPC, many research efforts are ongoing that concern scheduling and resource allocation in the context of cloud resources like container orchestration systems and the emerging compute continuum (for recent reviews see, e.g., [Carrion2022,

Carlini2023]). These efforts are relevant here due to the aforementioned expectation that it will become common practice to integrate HPC systems into federated digital infrastructures, which comprise various types of resources and may extend to the edge. A more recent development is scheduling in the context of Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) that support execution on HPC systems [Hudson2024].

Future challenge

For the future, we consider advanced scheduling algorithms to support co-scheduling of complex workflows, co-allocation for heterogeneous HPC systems, support of malleable jobs, multi-objective scheduling as well as scheduling and resource allocation in the context of federated and compute continuum infrastructures as a key challenge.

Challenge sub-topics

The need for co-scheduling will become more important due to upcoming complex workflows where different types of tasks that are (possibly tightly) coupled need to be scheduled on top of different types of resources, e.g. simulation tasks on CPU-only nodes and machine-learning tasks on accelerated nodes. Efficient utilisation of increasingly heterogeneous system architectures and the integration of low-capacity but fast storage resources close to the compute resources, co-allocation of resources has to become commonly supported. Utilisation of increasingly parallel hardware can be increased by supporting malleability, in particular, when workload resource requirements change over time. Supporting malleable jobs has a long history (see [DAmico2019] for a recent effort).

Interesting and in the future increasingly relevant cases for multi-objective resource allocation occur when both hardware utilisation should be maximised and power consumption needs to be kept within limits, which could become dynamic depending on availability of

electrical power. Scheduling and resource allocation taking service level objectives into account, which has already been established for cloud- and edge-computing (see, e.g., [Pusztai2022]), will generally become more relevant for HPC, e.g. to meet response time requirements for new types of applications like digital twins. With these being deployed in a federated infrastructure (see Destination Earth as a prominent example), scheduling and resource allocation has to happen in a context where services and resources are operated by different organisations where systems cannot be assumed to be cooperative.

To address the described challenges also the use of machine-learning models for scheduling decisions should be considered (for an earlier effort related to co-scheduling, see [Li2022]).

as a means for optimising numerical libraries and frameworks has attracted particular recent interest in the context of deep neural network (DNN) libraries like cuDNN or oneDNN and related DNN compilers (see [Li2021] for a recent survey and [Tollenaere2023] for a recent effort to optimise autotuning in this context). Given the large number of problem-size optimised kernels, this is a difficult problem that requires continuous optimisation efforts, which may not be affordable for new hardware architectures as can be seen for the case of the Arm-based A64FX processor [Kawakami2022]. Despite the very significant research efforts related to autotuning, many of the research results are not (yet) integrated into products.

Future challenge

The challenge identified in this context is the development and implementation of efficient autotuning mechanisms for key numerical libraries for upcoming hardware architectures and their vertical integration in HPC software stacks.

6.2 Autotuning

Rationale

The rationale for the topical area autotuning is that this has become a key technology in case of various numerical libraries, including libraries needed for machine learning. Adding timely and continuously improved support for new hardware architectures developed in Europe will be a major challenge.

State-of-the-art

Research on autotuning has a long history, in particular in the context of HPC applications [Balaprakash2018] and numerical libraries, with the latter resulting in solutions like the BLAS implementation ATLAS [Whaley2005] or FFT libraries like FFTW [Frigo1998]. Autotuning

7 Quantum and Hybrid Algorithms

Recent proof-of-concept demonstrations of quantum advantage using pseudo-random quantum sampling [Arute2019] and bosonic sampling [Zhong2020] suggest that quantum devices, as stand-alone pieces of hardware or paired with classical machines, could outperform the computational systems of classical computers alone in the future. Investigating this area of emerging technology presents two foundational challenges. First, developing use cases often relies on heuristic approaches, such as problem embedding in machine learning or quantum-state preparation. Second, demonstrating quantum advantage requires suitably hard tasks for quantum devices that are classically intractable for classical machines, even after intense development in the HPC community of the most powerful simulation techniques implemented in modern architectures.

7.1 Problem embedding, quantum-state preparation, error mitigation/correction

Problem Embedding: Much of the work focusing on the porting of classical problems to a quantum space has heavily relied on heuristics. Fundamentally, integration of a problem into a quantum computing context involves translating the problem to that over an n -qubit Hilbert space, i.e. $H=C^{2^n}$, for which a wide variety of encoding schemes have been developed. Typically, quantum algorithms have focused on the embedding of problems using continuous-valued complex entries in the Hilbert space, known as amplitude encoding.

While this method/approach makes many problems tractable from a human-reading perspective, we cannot assume, in general, that it will represent the most efficient or advantageous translation of a problem onto a quantum computing device. Indeed, a wider scope for problem encoding exists [Kahn2024], not just in the formulation of the amplitudes and choice of basis but in the deployment of the unitary operators used to solve the problem.

Future directions:

Encoding problems into a Hilbert space is not trivial. While amplitude encoding is usually seen as the natural way to encode analogue characteristics into the Hilbert space of a quantum system, alternative encoding schemes exist both in the state (vectors) and operators (such as Hamiltonians and unitaries). Moreover, loading data in as is non-trivial and generic state preparation is noted to be exponential in quantum resource usage. This motivates establishing a framework for identifying and translating problems most suitable to the constraints of quantum devices.

Error Mitigation Techniques are key in developing efficient quantum algorithms [Cai2023] and efficient approaches for error correction are required.

Future directions:

Develop robust error mitigation strategies for quantum computing systems, including methods to identify, quantify, and mitigate errors arising from noise and decoherence. Explore approaches such as error correction codes, error suppression techniques, and error-robust algorithms to enhance the reliability and scalability of quantum computations.

7.2 Algorithms on hybrid HPC/quantum architectures

In **Quantum Machine Learning**, the formulation of problems involves the application of feature maps, including heuristically developed circuits that are parameterised by classical variables. The deployment of such circuits can be found in the computation of kernels for Kernel-Support Vector Machines, where the advantage may come from the computation of classically intractable kernels. However, what combination of feature maps and datasets is expected to give a quantum advantage is an open

theoretical problem. Gradient descent optimisation for quantum variational algorithms has been noted for the “barren plateau” phenomenon in which calculated gradients vanish before reaching optimal parameters. It has been noted that attempts to avoid this may correspond to encoding in small subspaces that are amenable to simulation [Cerezo2024]. However, a stronger theoretical basis is needed to examine the relationships between feature map trainability and simulatability in general.

Future directions:

Variational and Quantum Machine Learning methods heavily rely on heuristic ansatz circuits $U(\Theta)$, where Θ is some vector of parameters of pre-selected length. It is typically unclear why or on which problems such circuits should be expected to yield any advantage beyond experimental benchmarks. It is thus reasonable to try to mathematically characterise the expressivity of circuits and its relation to classical data. Moreover, identifying the characteristics of loss functions that lead to barren plateaus and how to remedy these without crossing the threshold into classical simulatability remains a broad objective for feature map design.

In the area of **discrete optimisation**, graph formulations have been identified as cases displaying high classical complexity and featuring a natural interface between the node-edge formalism and the qubit topology of a quantum device. Naive formulations have focused on the idea of Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimisation (QUBO) where a problem is translated

into binary variables suitable for a quantum device, i.e. optimisation of a quadratic form on binary vectors [Symons2023]. In practical cases, constraints are a natural part of optimisation. One option has been to encode constraints through binary variables in the graph problems, but this introduces a heavy cost on the qubit count of a device and manifests heavily with problems at scale. Another approach is by embedding constraints into the unitary evolution of the circuit. For example, the classical-quantum algorithm used in Quantum Approximate Optimisation Algorithms (QAOA) and the more general Alternating Ansatz variant relies on a “mixer” Hamiltonian that has been noted to be able to encode constraints, as in the QED-inspired mixer for route optimisation [Zhang2021]. Development of these mixers is also performed heuristically. Therefore, there is a strong need for a more robust mathematical framework in describing and porting discrete optimisation problems onto a quantum computer. There is room to explore the embedding of a problem using the native topologies of quantum devices and the associated compiling of a problem to a graph problem. Even within frameworks like QAOA, there is scope for identifying Hamiltonian mixers that both adequately encode constraints and can be compiled into a set of unitary operations that do not incur a large cost in circuit depth.

Future directions:

Discrete optimisation tasks are often expressed in a graph formalism $G = (V, E)$, where V are nodes and E is a set of edges between the nodes. Many formulations have attempted to encode problems as an optimisation over binary strings, mapping strings to vectors in the Hilbert space. Such formulations have generally struggled with constraints, with problems defined under optimisation of a QUBO objective $f(x) = \sum_{ij} Q_{ij} x_i x_j, x_i \in \{0, 1\}$, Q upper triangular. Introducing constraints through additional binary variables can incur a large scaling penalty when the number of binary constraints grows with the problem. Quantum computers themselves offer their connective topology

describing the relationship between qubits. In the context of near-term devices, this motivates the development of graph formulations that map more easily to quantum computing topologies and are more efficient in resource usage. Moreover, most approaches to discrete optimisation on quantum computers are heuristic, highlighting the need to develop more robust strategies for encoding constraints in a quantum-native way as in the case of the Quantum Alternating Operator Ansatz.

Linear algebra for quantum computing and linear algebra on quantum computers: Linear algebraic formulations of problems are ubiquitous in physics, including numerical methods such as the discretisation of partial differential equations (PDEs). Quantum devices generally perform unitary operations natively, subject to decomposition into a native set of operations, which form only a restricted set of linear operators. A natural problem that has been considered is that of Hamiltonian simulation wherein one attempts to find a good unitary approximation of a Hamiltonian's evolution operator. Approaches have included expressing the Hamiltonian as a linear combination of unitaries (LCU) as well as Quantum Signal Processing (QSP) and more generally Quantum Singular Value Transformation (QSVT) that leverages eigenvalues (resp. spectral values) to compute functions of [An2023]. However, limitations exist when attempting to port essentially non-unitary descriptions to a quantum device, such as in open quantum systems. In porting such linear system problems to quantum devices it is best to leverage as much of the classical description as we can without resorting to direct computation of the (exponentially) sized matrix. Indeed, it may be further advantageous to find ways of computing and integrating common matrix computational steps such as QR and Singular Value Decomposition on the quantum device itself.

Future directions:

In general, linear algebra problems have been considered under the native representation of the Hilbert space. However, the native linear algebra operations on a quantum device are unitary, leading to a need to formulate the

problem in a unitary context. The most straightforward is a unitary embedding of a matrix A into a unitary over a higher dimensional space as

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} A & \mathbb{I} \\ \mathbb{I} & \mathbb{I} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Quantum Signal Processing and QSVT methods generally rely on the spectral properties of such matrices. This motivates some discussion on how best to avoid any classical computation over large matrices, including attempts to native decomposition steps such as QR or SVD. There is also room to avoid reliance on spectral methods, especially where accurate unitary characterisations might prove difficult in a noisy regime [Wang2023]. Implementations of linear combinations of unitaries generally involve the conditioning of the unitaries on an ancilla qubit register. The method generally involves non-deterministic post-selection on the ancilla, motivating amplitude amplification steps to maximise the probability that the linear combination is implemented. This in turn incurs a cost in circuit runs and depth. As a result, there is room to consider alternative or more efficient ways to embed such combinations in a circuit.

Stochastic Computations and Quantum Monte Carlo. As probabilistic machines, quantum computing has naturally been identified as a means of performing stochastic sampling. Quantum Monte Carlo is a classical group of methods that attempt to model the behaviour of many-body quantum systems through classical Monte Carlo methods. An identified bottleneck in such methods is that of the “sign

problem” where oscillating terms resulting from classical simulation require an exponential increase in sampling. It is therefore natural to consider how a quantum circuit can be used in generating Monte Carlo samples.

Future directions:

As probabilistic machines, quantum computers have a natural application in stochastic sampling. Monte Carlo methods are widely used in stochastic sampling, involving the use of repeated samples from a probability distribution. In principle, the operation of a quantum computer corresponds to the generation of (quasi)probability distributions. “Quantum Monte Carlo” refers to a classical suite of Monte Carlo methods for estimates of many-body quantum systems [Rinaldi2022]. However, it has been noted that models of wave functions lead to the sign problem due to oscillatory contributions. Yang et al. [Yang2021] propose a means of tackling the sign problem by modelling the wave function using quantum computing resources. More generally, applications of quantum computing to Monte Carlo integration have been proposed [Shimada2020]. We note here that there is room for theoretical explorations of the distributions generated under quantum dynamics and deeper explorations of how quantum computing methods can enhance stochastic methods in general.

Future directions:

Quantum circuits currently implemented in real Quantum hardware can be simulated in classical computers. Recently, however, this trend may start to diverge by identifying proper circuits that cannot be simulated [King2024]. At the same time, novel techniques and tools in HPC allow faster simulation [Zhao2024]. A crucial direction of research is to identify how the families of easy problems for each technology relate to the other, helping to define the boundary between classical and Quantum computing resources.

7.3 Simulation of quantum circuits

The simulation of Quantum circuits and Quantum systems is in general a hard task for classical computers. The development of novel simulation techniques has been identified as a critical task with an impact on Quantum algorithm development, allowing the possibility of testing heuristics in realistic scenarios. Moreover, the simulation of Quantum systems is a well-suited problem for HPC architectures with a positive gain in performance. The recent formulation of the simulation problem in the language of Tensor Networks has provided the most competitive results. Dedicated libraries are currently under development, as novel techniques proposed recently have been improving results obtained from Quantum hardware [Zhao2024].

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